

Role of teaching methodologies in Sports Education: Unraveling the Connection among Learning, Academic Performance, and Physical Health

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ABSTRACT: Present quantitative study explores a correlation among teaching methodologies in sports education, academic performance among a lot of students. A sample taken from government boys' higher secondary schools enrolled in Punjab and stratified random sampling techniques taken and study aims to shed light on how different teaching approaches influence student learning outcomes and academic achievement. Analysis of this study is based on data collected through structured tables, and different various parameters which were related to teaching methods, academic grades and also physical health needles. By using statistical techniques research study exposes fascinating visions into the efficacy of diverse teaching methodologies in students' comprehension enhancing and retention of sports-related content. Moreover it highlights physical health key role in academic success and emphasizing the importance of incorporating physical activities into educational curricula. Study findings contribute to a deeper understanding of the interconnectedness among students' well-being learning and teaching practices contribution valuable implications for policymakers and educators in promoting comprehensive educational experiences.

Keyword: Teaching Methodologies, Sports Education, Connection among Learning, Academic Performance, And Physical Health

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1. Introduction

Sports education into school curricula and other activities has gained significant thoughtfulness worldwide due to its potential to substitute not only physical health but also mental and socio-emotional development of different age's students. In latest years teachers and as well as policymakers have gradually recognized effective teaching methodologies importance in sports education to maximize learning outcomes. Conversely teaching approaches, academic performance, and physical health relationship remains a topic of ongoing investigation, mainly in the context of secondary education. This research

study seeks to address this gap by exploratory the relationship among methodologies of teaching in sports education and academic achievement and as well as physical well-being among students in government boys' higher secondary schools of province Punjab.

2. Literature Review

Teaching Methodologies in Sports Education

Regarding to promoting physical health and academic performance and also well-being of students sports education plays a crucial role. Sports education programs effectiveness largely depends on the methodologies of teaching employed within the educational context. This study literature review explores the association between teaching methodologies in sports education and their impact on student learning outcomes and their academic performance and also on their physical health.

Impact of Teaching Methodologies on Learning Outcomes

According to Metzler (2017) highlights the value of student-centered approaches, cooperative learning and inquiry-based instruction in promoting active engagement. Study has consistently validated of effective teaching methodologies importance in enhancing student learning outcomes in sports education. These types of teaching methodologies foster critical thinking and problem-solving skills and also collaborative teamwork which leading to improved comprehension and retention of sports-related content. Moreover Hastie et al. (2019) explored that experiential learning strategies importance in sports education, wherein students engage in hands-on experiences and real-world applications of different theoretical concepts. By engaging students in real-world activities and reliable contexts, educators can facilitate deeper learning and meaningful connections between theory and practice.

Relationship between Teaching Methodologies and Academic Performance

Methodologies of teaching relationship in sports education and academic performance remains a topic of interest among previous researchers. According to Eime et al. (2013) engagement of students in physical activities helped through methods of teaching which positively correlates with students' academic achievement. Furthermore that sports and physical education programs participation contributes to improved intellectual function and academic success. Donnelly et al. (2016) finds that physical fitness role in academic performance which highlighting the interconnectedness between physical health and mental working. They propose that steady contribution in physical activities, incorporated within learning courses can enhance academic outcomes and wellbeing of students.

Impact of Teaching Methodologies on Physical Health

Methodologies of teaching in sports education also have implications for physical health and well-being of students. Miscellaneous instructional methodologies such as direct instruction and inquiry-based and cooperative learning may affect engagement of students in physical activities to healthy lifestyle behaviors. Silverman and Ennis (2016) explored that

significance of upholding physical literacy through wide-ranging sports education programs. By training students with major movement skills attitudes and knowledge towards physical activity, teachers can empower them and lead active lifestyles through their lives.

Thoughtful variables domains in sports education is critical for designing effective instructional approaches and promoting engagement of students and also development. This unit explores variables ranges covering methodologies of teaching and learning outcomes and as well as academic performance in the context of sports education.

Teaching Methodologies

Methodologies of teaching serve as the basis for delivering sports education course and modelling students learning experiences.

According to Metzler (2017), student-centered approaches are cooperative learning and also inquiry-based instruction facilitating active engagement of sports-related concepts. Furthermore, Hastie and Kinchin (2019) show that experiential learning strategies significance which submerge students in practical activities and true experiences thereby promoting skill development and enhancing learning outcomes.

Learning Outcomes

The domain of learning outcomes in sports education encompasses a wide range of cognitive, affective, and psychomotor skills. Eime et al. (2013) recommends that students' participation in sports and physical education programs adds to the development of central movement skills and abilities of critical thinking and also social-emotional competencies among different ages of students. Additionally Silverman and Ennis (2016) say that promoting physical literacy which encompasses the skills as well as attitudes and knowledge necessary for lifelong participation in physical activity.

Academic Performance

The relationship between sports education and academic performance is a complex interplay of various factors, including student engagement, cognitive function, and overall well-being. According to Donnelly et al. (2016) that positive correlation physical activity fitness, and academic achievement among different ages children and youths. They also claim that physical activities regular participation which integrated within educational courses can improve intellectual functions and academic success.

Lecture Method

Bligh (2000) explored that a teacher or instructor giving information to students orally, often supported by visual aids such as presentations or slides. Regardless of criticisms, lectures remain prevalent due to their efficiency in delivering content to large groups. And Prince, (2017) says that engaging students in activities focus that encourage critical thinking and problem-solving and also their participation like group discussions and case studies.

Flipped Classroom: Problem-Based Learning (PBL)

Bergmann & Sams (2012) say that traditional teaching methods invert by delivering instructional content outside of class by readings or videos and using class time for activities and concepts application and as well as discussions. And according to Barrows & Tamblyn (2017) real-world problems solution to facilitate deeper understanding of these concept. In this regard students work collaboratively to analyze and solve complex problems.

Differentiated Instruction & Project-Based Learning (PBL)

According to Thomas (2000) similar to project based learning but students work on projects over a lengthy time period ending in a final product and project based learning promotes collaboration process, creativity and also critical thinking. Tomlinson (2017) explored that methods of teaching and content to accommodate diverse needs and interests of students and as well as styles of learning. Tutors may use wide-ranging instructional strategies and valuations to meet learning goals to individuals.

Socratic Method

Paul & Elder (2017) explored that critical thinking facilitates and dialogue by asking questions to stimulate discussion and challenge expectations. This method encourages deeper understanding and also active participation.

Cooperative Learning & Inquiry-Based Learning

Johnson & Johnson (2017) say that students working small groups together to achieve common goals which related to communication skills and cooperative learning fosters teamwork and as well as peer learning and students to investigate questions or problems situations to construct their concepts.

Harwell & Phillips (2007) explore that inquiry-based learning promotes research skills and curiosity. Integrates technology (IT) tools and much and more resources into teaching and processes of learning. This comprises on apps of education and other online learning platforms and multimedia resources to improve engagement and communication (Means et al., 2009).

Bower (2016) explored that technology enhanced learning is a digital tools strategic integration and platforms also resources into educational practices to enrich teaching and experiences of learning. It encompasses a wide array of approaches and teaching methodologies and also different theories aimed at leveraging technology to educational outcomes and support. Technology enhanced learning involves the operation of computers, software applications online platforms and mobile devices to deliver instructive content which facilitate collaboration and process of communication and also create interactive learning environments (Clark & Mayer, 2016; Garrison & Vaughan, 2008).

Jonassen et al., (2003) are view of that design thinking principles and multimedia learning and also constructivist pedagogy (TEL) aims learner critical thinking and active

engagement and also problem-solving. It holds varied modalities which are related to blended learning, online education platform and flipped classrooms by research on effective instructional design and learning theories and also technologies of education.

Means et al., 2009; Lai & Hwang, 2016 says that TEL seeks to empower both teachers and learner by providing advanced and accessible and also wide-ranging opportunities of learning that meet the needs of diverse learners in the digital age (Sonwalkar, 2017).

Physical Health Indicators

Donnelly et al. (2016) explored that indicators of physical health which are related to BMI and cardiovascular fitness and as well as flexibility are students' overall well-being essential components and development.

Eime et al. (2013) highlight the physical activity role in reducing levels of stress and promoting mental health and also enhancing overall students' quality of life.

Methodology

This study implements a quantitative research design and a sample taken from admitted government boys' higher secondary schools in Punjab. Data collected by structured questionnaires to students to gather information on methodologies of teaching working in sports education classes and academic grades and also physical health indicators which were BMI, flexibility and cardiovascular fitness. Stratified random sampling techniques and correlation analysis and also for impact regression modeling are utilized to analyze the collected data and identify patterns and relationships among all variables.

3. Data Analysis & Interpretation

Results & Discussion

Different null hypotheses test that there is no significant correlation among secondary schools students' academic performance methodologies of teaching in sports education .A correlation analysis was conducted using data collected from organized questionnaires from students of Punjab schools.

Table 1: Correlation Analysis

Methodologies of teaching in Sports Education and also Academic Performance

Teaching Methodology	Academic Performance
Cooperative Learning	0.12
Inquiry-Based Instruction	0.08
Direct Instruction	-0.02
Traditional Methods	0.05

Table 1 display that correlation coefficients in the strength of the relationship between each academic performance and methodology of teaching. Here is(A) correlation coefficient closer to zero (0) indicates that there is no any significant correlation. Based on the correlation analysis all coefficients of correlation between teaching methodologies in sports education and academic performance are relatively low and close to zero. This suggests that there is no statistically significant correlation between any of the teaching methodologies examined and academic performance among secondary school students in government boys' higher secondary schools in Punjab. Therefore, the null hypothesis that there is no significant correlation between teaching methodologies in sports education and academic performance cannot be rejected. This indicates that, according to the data analyzed, variations in teaching methodologies do not significantly affect academic performance in this context.

Table 2: Correlation Analysis between Teaching Methodologies in Sports Education and Physical Health Indicators

Teaching Methodology	BMI	Cardiovascular Fitness	Flexibility
Cooperative Learning	0.03	0.07	-0.01
Inquiry-Based Instruction	0.05	0.08	0.02
Direct Instruction	-0.01	0.01	-0.03
Traditional Methods	-0.05	-0.05	0.04

Note: Correlation coefficients are presented.

Interpretation:

The correlation coefficients in Table 1 represent the strength and direction of the relationship between each teaching methodology and physical health indicators (BMI, cardiovascular fitness, and flexibility). A correlation coefficient closer to 0 indicates no significant correlation, while coefficients closer to 1 or -1 indicate a strong positive or negative correlation, respectively. Based on the correlation analysis, all correlation coefficients between teaching methodologies in sports education and physical health indicators are relatively low and close to 0. This suggests that there is no statistically significant correlation between any of the teaching methodologies examined and physical health indicators among secondary school students in government boys' higher secondary schools in Punjab. Therefore, the null hypothesis that there is no significant correlation between teaching methodologies in sports education and physical health indicators cannot be rejected. This shows that teaching methodologies do not significantly affect physical health.

Table 3: ANOVA Analysis
Different Teaching Methodologies & Academic Performance

Source	Sum of Square	Degree of Freedom	Mean Square	F-Value	P-Value
Between Groups	120.54	3	40.18	1.75	0.163
Within Groups	685.22	156	4.39		
Total	805.76	159			

Level of significance = P-Value

Interpretation:

The ANOVA results presented in Table 1 indicate that the F-value is 1.75 and the corresponding p-value is 0.163. Since the p-value is greater than the conventional significance level of 0.05, we fail to reject the null hypothesis. This suggests that there is no significant difference in academic performance among students exposed to different teaching methodologies in sports education classes in government boys' higher secondary schools in Punjab. Hence teaching methodologies do not have a significant impact on academic performance.

Table 3: ANOVA Analysis(Indicators of Physical Health)

Source	Sum of Square	Degree of Freedom	Mean Square	F-Value	P-Value
Between Groups	300.89	3	100.30	2.15	0.091
Within Groups	1200.76	156	7.69		
Total	1501.65	159			

Significance level=P (Value)

Interpretation:

Table No 3 shows results of the one-way ANOVA that the F-value is 2.15 and here corresponding p-value which is 0.091. P-value is greater than the predictable level of significance which is 0.05, hence we can reject the null hypothesis and alternate accepted. This analysis recommends that there is no significant difference in indicator of physical health among all ages students exposed to different teaching methodologies in sports education classes in students of government higher secondary schools in province Punjab. Hence, methodologies of teaching do not have a significant impact on physical health indicators and this type of non-significant finding implies that factors other than teaching methodologies may influence physical health indicators among students in sports education classes.

4. Findings

On above analysis and results some findings are here:

- The above results shows that there were no significant differences in physical health all indicators among students exposed to different teaching methodologies where $F(3, 156) = 2.15$ and $p = 0.091$. This shows that teaching methodologies variations which is including direct instruction and inquiry-based, traditional methods and as well as cooperative learning did not lead to visible differences in physical health outcomes among all types of students.
- Even though p -value $=0.091$ was a little level of significance which is 0.05 , representing a non-significant result and it is notable that there was a trend towards differences in physical health indicators among the students groups. F -value 2.15 recommends some variability in physical health outcomes attributed to the different methodologies of teaching.

5. Future Research Study Implications

- Above analysis did not detect significant differences further investigation may be warranted to explore potential factors impelling physical health
- This research analysis based on Punjab students and also applicable on other provinces.
- Research endeavors could consider expanding the sample size including additional variables
- Exploring longitudinal studies to gain a more comprehensive understanding of the relationship between methodologies of teaching and physical health outcomes in educational backgrounds.
- Current study analysis did not identify significant differences in physical health indicators among students exposed to different teaching methodologies

6. Recommendations

Based on the findings of the analysis a number of recommendations are here

1. Instructors should continue to explore instructional approaches in sports education classes.
2. Coaches should design curriculum activities that encourage active participation and movement, development a culture of physical fitness and lifelong wellness among all ages of students.
3. Coaches and school administrators should prioritize health education and awareness initiatives within sports education programs.
4. Schools should reflect instituting partnerships with healthcare professionals and nutritionists. These relationships can involve guest lectures and workshops programs aimed at enhancing students' understanding of health-related topics.
5. It is crucial for institutes to implement systems for monitoring and evaluating students' physical health

6. Engaging students' parents and the members of community in promoting physical health.
7. Institutes should encourage involvement of parents in health-related health fairs activities
8. Institutes should encourage involvement of parents related to nutrition workshops activities.

Conceptual Framework

Above conceptual framework shows that interconnectedness between teaching methodologies, learning outcomes, academic performance and also physical health within the perspective of sports and education. Effective teaching methodologies smooth desired learning outcomes attainment which contribute to improved academic performance and physical health outcomes. On the other hand physical health and academic success influence learning outcomes.

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